

Supplementary Table 1 List of used primers. Each binding site is listed

Name	Target	Accession number	Position	Direction	Usage	Sequence, 5' - 3' direction
1007	CVF SwC-H RNA1B	MG925372	336 – 357	reverse	5' RACE	GATGCCITTTTGACTTTCAT
1009	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2C	KX192393	903 – 922	reverse	sequencing	ATTTTGCAACCAATCCGT
1010	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2C	KX192393	805 – 823	reverse	sequencing	CATGCCATAAACCACTGGA
1010	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2B	KX192392	828 – 846	reverse	sequencing	CATGCCATAAACCACTGGA
1011	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2B	KX192392	757 – 776	reverse	sequencing	TGATTGCCACCAAGTCTGT
1012	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2B	KX192392	481 – 502	reverse	5' RACE	GRAAYGCCATCYTTTCAAGCTT
1012	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2C	KX192393	458 – 479	reverse	5' RACE	GRAAYGCCATCYTTTCAAGCTT
1012	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2B	KX192392	481 – 502	reverse	5' RACE	GRAAYGCCATCYTTTCAAGCTT
1012	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2C	KX192393	458 – 479	reverse	5' RACE	GRAAYGCCATCYTTTCAAGCTT
1013	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2B	KX192392	3182 – 3202	forward	3' RACE	GAAGTGATCCAAAAACAATA
1014	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2A	KX192391	891 – 910	reverse	sequencing	ACCATCCACAAAATCTCTA
1015	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1C	KX192390	642 – 664	reverse	5' RACE	CTGTGCACITTTTCATAGTCACA
1016	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1C	KX192390	5300 – 5319	forward	sequencing	AGGAGTGCATGGACCTACGT
1017	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	798 – 818	reverse	5' RACE	TATGCTCCGCCACAGCTTGA
1018	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	862 – 881	reverse	5' RACE	AGACCCATAACAACACTATC
1018	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	857 – 876	reverse	5' RACE	AGACCCATAACAACACTATC
1019	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	803 – 825	reverse	5' RACE	TATATGTTCTGCCAAAAGTTTAA
1020	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	613 – 635	reverse	5' RACE	AAAGATGCACAYGARGACATAAG
1020	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1C	KX192390	601 – 623	reverse	5' RACE	AAAGATGCACAYGARGACATAAG
1020	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	608 – 630	reverse	5' RACE	AAAGATGCACAYGARGACATAAG
1029	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2C	KX192393	268 – 289	reverse	5' RACE	CTCCTCGTATTCAAGCCAAGTT
1030	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2B	KX192392	318 – 339	reverse	5' RACE	CACGAACGTGGATGTGTAATCA
1031	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2A	KX192391	301 – 321	reverse	5' RACE	GACACAAACGTAAAGGTTCTGA
1034	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	990 – 1012	reverse	5' RACE	AGCTTTRTAWCCACATATAGCTC
1034	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	995 – 1017	reverse	5' RACE	AGCTTTRTAWCCACATATAGCTC
1037	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	5 – 27	forward	nearly complete segment amplification	TAAGAGATTAACAACCCGCTTTC
1037	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1C	KX192390	5 – 27	forward	nearly complete segment amplification	TAAGAGATTAACAACCCGCTTTC
1037	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2C	KX192393	5 – 27	forward	nearly complete segment amplification	TAAGAGATTAACAACCCGCTTTC
1037	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2A	KX192391	5 – 27	forward	nearly complete segment amplification	TAAGAGATTAACAACCCGCTTTC
1037	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2B	KX192392	5 – 27	forward	nearly complete segment amplification	TAAGAGATTAACAACCCGCTTTC
1037	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	5 – 27	forward	nearly complete segment amplification	TAAGAGATTAACAACCCGCTTTC
1038	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2C	KX192393	3725 – 3744	reverse	nearly complete segment amplification	GCTTTCACCAATTCTCAACA
1038	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	6132 – 6151	reverse	nearly complete segment amplification	GCTTTCACCAATTCTCAACA
1038	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2A	KX192391	3571 – 3590	reverse	nearly complete segment amplification	GCTTTCACCAATTCTCAACA
1038	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	6134 – 6153	reverse	nearly complete segment amplification	GCTTTCACCAATTCTCAACA
1038	CVF SwC-H RNA1B	MG925372	6157 – 6176	reverse	nearly complete segment amplification	GCTTTCACCAATTCTCAACA
1038	CVF SwC-H RNA2	MG925373	3828 – 3847	reverse	nearly complete segment amplification	GCTTTCACCAATTCTCAACA
1038	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2B	KX192392	3434 – 3453	reverse	nearly complete segment amplification	GCTTTCACCAATTCTCAACA
1039	CVF SwC-H RNA2	MG925373	139 – 159	forward	5' RACE	TGGTTACCAAGCCCTCATT
1083	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	103 – 120	forward	nearly complete segment amplification	GTGGTTACTCGTGCCTT
1083	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	98 – 115	forward	nearly complete segment amplification	GTGGTTACTCGTGCCTT
1083	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1C	KX192390	95 – 112	forward	nearly complete segment amplification	GTGGTTACTCGTGCCTT
1150	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1C	KX192390	3408 – 3430	forward	sequencing	GGATAGTGAACCTGCAGTATATC
1406	CVF SwC-H RNA1B	MG925372	369 – 388	reverse	5' RACE	GTGCACCCAAAGAACATCTT
1407	CVF SwC-H RNA2	MG925373	282 – 301	reverse	5' RACE	TCCTCACTGTCTCGTACTC
1408	CVF SwC-H RNA2	MG925373	382 – 401	reverse	5' RACE	AACAAGGAATGAGCAACGT
1409	CVF SwC-H RNA2	MG925373	848 – 867	reverse	sequencing	AAGGAACAGGCACATCAATC
1445	CVF SwC-H RNA2	MG925373	274 – 295	reverse	5' RACE	ACTGTCTCGTACTCTCCCTTGA
1446	CVF SwC-H RNA1A	MG925371	5890 – 5911	forward	3' RACE	CAGCAAAACAAGAATCTGGGAT
1447	CVF SwC-H RNA1B	MG925372	222 – 242	reverse	5' RACE	AGAACCATCAGAGTGAATGCT
1448	CVF SwC-H RNA1A	MG925371	429 – 449	reverse	5' RACE	TCTGAGACAAGAAGGGTTGGA
1449	CVF SwC-H RNA1B	MG925372	5837 – 5856	forward	3' RACE	TTGTGGAGCCTTGGCTGTAG
1450	CVF SwC-H RNA1A	MG925371	5984 – 6003	forward	3' RACE	TTCCAGTGTGTTGGCAGACA
1450	CVF SwC-H RNA1B	MG925372	6004 – 6023	forward	sequencing	TTCCAGTGTGTTGGCAGACA
1450	CVF SwC-H RNA2	MG925373	3354 – 3373	forward	3' RACE	TTCCAGTGTGTTGGCAGACA
1451	CVF SwC-H RNA2	MG925373	3281 – 3300	forward	sequencing	TGTCAGCATTGCCACTCTCT
1452	CVF SwC-H RNA1B	MG925372	138 – 156	reverse	5' RACE	GAAATGAGGGCTTGGGTAA
1452	CVF SwC-H RNA1A	MG925371	163 – 181	reverse	5' RACE	GAAATGAGGGCTTGGGTAA
1542	CVF SwC-H RNA2	MG925373	589 – 608	reverse	5' RACE	AGATGTTATAGTCGAGAAG

1543	CVF SwC-H RNA1A	MG925371	303 – 323	reverse	5' RACE	TCATCAAGATCCACAATTCCC
1544	CVF SwC-H RNA1A	MG925371	223 – 241	reverse	5' RACE	CACAAATCAGCTGGAACACA
1562	CVF SwC-H RNA2	MG925373	1614 – 1633	forward	sequencing	GAAGTTGAGATGAGTATGCC
1632	CVF SwC-H RNA1A	MG925371	100 – 119	reverse	5' RACE	TCAACCAAAGAGCAGACGAA
818	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2B	KX192392	3153 – 3173	reverse	sequencing	CCTCCAGCACTTCCAGAAACA
819	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2B	KX192392	2621 – 2644	forward	sequencing	GTGGATACCCTTTCTCTGCATCTC
820	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	4411 – 4431	reverse	sequencing	ACACTCGATTCCCACTC
821	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	4238 – 4262	reverse	sequencing	CCTTCGAAAGTCCCTATCACTAGAG
822	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	3983 – 4004	forward	sequencing	CCTGTGAAAAGATACCCAGCGT
823	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	3651 – 3673	forward	sequencing	GATACCTCGTTTCATGACCTACG
827	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2C	KX192393	220 – 238	forward	5' RACE	GGGCTTTGAAACATACGCT
827	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2C	KX192393	220 – 238	forward	5' RACE	GGGCTTTGAAACATACGCT
829	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2B	KX192392	1426 – 1446	forward	sequencing	CTTCAATTTGACAATCCGAAC
829	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2C	KX192393	1403 – 1423	forward	sequencing	CTTCAATTTGACAATCCGAAC
830	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2B	KX192392	1421 – 1442	reverse	sequencing	GGATTGTCAAATGAAGAACA
830	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2C	KX192393	1398 – 1419	reverse	sequencing	GGATTGTCAAATGAAGAACA
833	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	5828 – 5845	forward	sequencing	AGGGAGGATTGCAACGTC
834	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	5824 – 5842	reverse	sequencing	GTTCGAATCCTCCTCTTTG
835	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	4343 – 4359	forward	sequencing	CCCGATTCAAAGTTGC
838	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	2556 – 2579	forward	sequencing	TTGAAAGGGCATCTTGTATGTGT
839	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	1307 – 1328	reverse	sequencing	TGTCTAAACACCAATTCTGAG
840	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	1307 – 1329	forward	sequencing	CTCAGAATTGGGTGTTAGACAG
841	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1C	KX192390	267 – 285	forward	5' RACE	CACCTTCACTTTGGTTGCT
850	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2C	KX192393	326 – 343	reverse	5' RACE	ACGCTTACAGGGAGTGAG
851	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2C	KX192393	217 – 239	reverse	5' RACE	CAGCGTATGTTTCAAGCCCGTA
853	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	439 – 456	reverse	5' RACE	ATGTCCACCCTCATCC
854	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1C	KX192390	269 – 291	reverse	5' RACE	ACCTCCAGCAACCAAGTGAAGG
857	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	1068 – 1088	forward	sequencing	TGGTCAAAGGATCATGCATGG
870	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2A	KX192391	1634 – 1655	reverse	sequencing	CTGCCATAGAGAAGGAGCCAG
871	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1C	KX192390	23 – 48	forward	sequencing	CTTTCGATACCAGCTCTTCTTAAAGC
927	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1C	KX192390	3479 – 3501	forward	sequencing	TTTTTGATGGAGAGAGATCTT
930	CVF SwC-H RNA1B	MG925372	3556 – 3578	forward	sequencing	TCCTTTCATACAAGTATTATGCT
931	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1C	KX192390	3563 – 3586	forward	RNA1 universal	TTCCYGARATTGCYAAGATWGATG
931	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	3575 – 3598	forward	RNA1 universal	TTCCYGARATTGCYAAGATWGATG
931	CVF SwC-H RNA1B	MG925372	3595 – 3618	forward	RNA1 universal	TTCCYGARATTGCYAAGATWGATG
931	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1C	KX192390	3563 – 3586	forward	RNA1 universal	TTCCYGARATTGCYAAGATWGATG
931	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	3570 – 3593	forward	RNA1 universal	TTCCYGARATTGCYAAGATWGATG
932	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	5059 – 5081	reverse	RNA1 universal	ATRGTKATRTGSADYTTKKCCAT
932	CVF SwC-H RNA1B	MG925372	5079 – 5101	reverse	RNA1 universal	ATRGTKATRTGSADYTTKKCCAT
932	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1C	KX192390	5047 – 5069	reverse	RNA1 universal	ATRGTKATRTGSADYTTKKCCAT
932	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	5054 – 5076	reverse	RNA1 universal	ATRGTKATRTGSADYTTKKCCAT
932	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1C	KX192390	5047 – 5069	reverse	RNA1 universal	ATRGTKATRTGSADYTTKKCCAT
933	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1C	KX192390	5056 – 5078	reverse	sequencing	CCATCTGTAATGGTTATGTGCAA
935	CVF SwC-H RNA1B	MG925372	5145 – 5168	reverse	sequencing	GAGAAAATCGCACTTGTCAAGAGT
950	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2C	KX192393	3092 – 3114	forward	3' RACE, RNA2 universal	GGHHWVAYWCTYATGGCYAARTT
950	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2B	KX192392	3115 – 3137	forward	3' RACE, RNA2 universal	GGHHWVAYWCTYATGGCYAARTT
950	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2A	KX192391	3095 – 3117	forward	3' RACE, RNA2 universal	GGHHWVAYWCTYATGGCYAARTT
951	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	5570 – 5591	forward	sequencing	CRAAYGACTATGTTGTTGGCT
951	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	5565 – 5586	forward	sequencing	CRAAYGACTATGTTGTTGGCT
952	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1C	KX192390	4759 – 4778	reverse	RNA1 universal	GCCATBARNAGATTYCTCG
952	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	4766 – 4785	reverse	RNA1 universal	GCCATBARNAGATTYCTCG
952	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	4771 – 4790	reverse	RNA1 universal	GCCATBARNAGATTYCTCG
953	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2C	KX192393	3269 – 3292	reverse	sequencing	GRAGARYCAAACAGAATARGTGTC
953	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2B	KX192392	3296 – 3319	reverse	sequencing	GRAGARYCAAACAGAATARGTGTC
953	CVF SwC-H RNA1B	MG925372	6020 – 6043	reverse	RNA2 universal	GRAGARYCAAACAGAATARGTGTC
953	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	5994 – 6017	reverse	RNA2 universal	GRAGARYCAAACAGAATARGTGTC
953	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	5996 – 6019	reverse	sequencing	GRAGARYCAAACAGAATARGTGTC
953	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2A	KX192391	3284 – 3307	reverse	RNA2 universal	GRAGARYCAAACAGAATARGTGTC
954	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2C	KX192393	1557 – 1577	forward	sequencing	CTGGTGAATGACCCAGCGTG
957	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2C	KX192393	3234 – 3258	reverse	3' RACE	CTGGAAAATCTCCAGTAGTCCAAT
957	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2C	KX192393	3234 – 3258	reverse	3' RACE	CTGGAAAATCTCCAGTAGTCCAAT
958	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2C	KX192393	1308 – 1333	forward	sequencing	CAAATATTTCCATCCGTTTGGTAGG

959	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2B	KX192392	1532 – 1557	forward	sequencing	AAGCTGTTTCTCTTTGGAAGTTGAA
960	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2B	KX192392	3354 – 3376	reverse	3' RACE	CAGGTGGGACTCGAAATCCAACG
960	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	6052 – 6074	reverse	3' RACE	CAGGTGGGACTCGAAATCCAACG
960	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	6054 – 6076	reverse	3' RACE	CAGGTGGGACTCGAAATCCAACG
961	PrVF SwC-43 RNA2A	KX192391	1637 – 1664	forward	sequencing	GCTTCTTCTCTATGGCAGATGTTATAT
962	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	4548 – 4570	forward	sequencing	TTCTCATGAARARAAGRAGTGTG
962	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1C	KX192390	4541 – 4563	forward	sequencing	TTCTCATGAARARAAGRAGTGTG
991	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1C	KX192390	5869 – 5889	forward	sequencing	AGTTTGGGTATCTTCTCTGAA
992	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	5321 – 5342	forward	sequencing	TAAACTGCGAAGAAAAGCTCT
993	PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	5277 – 5297	forward	sequencing	TTTTGCGAGAACCTTTTCTAC
994	CVF SwC-H RNA1B	MG925372	5835 – 5853	forward	3' RACE	CGTTGTGGAGCCTTGCTG
123Up	CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	172-191	reverse	sequencing	ACTCTCACGTTGGTTGTAGG
622Do	CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	656-679	forward	sequencing	CAAGAACATTGTAGACATGAGGAC
422up	CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	482-502	reverse	sequencing	TTGCTTCTCAGTCTTCATCCT
728do	CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	768-788	forward	sequencing	GCCAGGCCATCACGACACAT
622UP	CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	656-679	reverse	sequencing	GTCCTCATGTCTACAATGTTCTTG
847do	CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	987-1006	forward	sequencing	CCAGTAGAGACATGCAGGAG
826UP	CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	886-906	reverse	sequencing	ACATTTTCTATTGGGGCTGTT
1118DO	CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	1158-1178	forward	sequencing	ATAAAAGCTGCCATTGTTCT
847Up	CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	987-1006	reverse	sequencing	CTCCTGCATGTCTACTGG
1760Do	CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	1795-1816	forward	sequencing	TTTGTGTGAGTGAGCTTTTCC
1568UP	CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	1628-1649	reverse	sequencing	GCAGTGTTTTCATAGGAAGTGA
1850DO	CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	1628-1649	forward	sequencing	CGACGATAGCCAGACCAAAA
1760UP	CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	1795-1816	reverse	sequencing	GGAAAAGCTCACTCACACAAA
2546DO	CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	2602-2626	forward	sequencing	CCAATTGATGATTAGGCAGAACA
2464UP	CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	2524-2544	reverse	sequencing	GTGACTCTTGTGGGATTGTC
2671DO	CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	2713-2733	forward	sequencing	CTTTCGGGTGATGATCAGG
2546Up	CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	2602-2626	reverse	sequencing	TGTTCTGCCTAATCATCAAATGG
3299Do	CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	3338-3357	forward	sequencing	CCGATAGACAGCCAACCTCAC
3140Up	CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	3198-3220	reverse	sequencing	TGTTCTGCCTAATCATCAAATGG
3865Do	CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	3899-3923	forward	sequencing	GTTATTACGCTGGGTATCTTTTCAC
3530Up	CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	3588-3609	reverse	sequencing	TGCTGAAACTATAGACGGTGAC
4391Do	CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	4429-4449	forward	sequencing	GAATTTTCATGCGCACAAACAAG
4263Up	CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	4321-4341	reverse	sequencing	CCTGAACTGGTTGGAATCGAG
5103Do	CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	5140-5160	forward	sequencing	TTCAAGGTTACGCGTGTGAC
4939UP	CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	4979-5001	reverse	sequencing	AAATGCACATCACCATCACTGAT
CVF-3UTR do	CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	5925-5945	forward	sequencing	AGCAGGCYTGAGAGCCAAAC
141UP	CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA2	LT991640	141-161	reverse	sequencing	GTGGTTACCAAAGCCCTCATT
712DO	CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA2	LT991640	800-820	forward	sequencing	ACATTTTCAATTGCGCTGGTG
571Up	CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA2	LT991640	679-699	reverse	sequencing	CCTACCGTGAACAGCTTCCCTC
1325Do	CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA2	LT991640	1411-1433	forward	sequencing	AACAGATCTTGAGAAGGGTATGG
951Up	CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA2	LT991640	1059-1080	reverse	sequencing	CAAGATGCGCGTAATGCTTTTC
1850Do	CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA2	LT991640	1941-1961	forward	sequencing	ACAAGCGGGATTCCAAAAGAC
1724Up	CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA2	LT991640	1835-1854	reverse	sequencing	TTTGATTCTCTCCTGCGTGTG
2515Do	CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA2	LT991640	2605-2626	forward	sequencing	ACACTAGAAGTCAACGCTATCAC
2425UP	CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA2	LT991640	2539-2561	reverse	sequencing	CCAATTCTGCTAGTGTCAATCAT
R2-3END R	CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA2	LT991640	3887-3906	forward	sequencing	TGGGCTTTCACCATCTCA

Supplementary Table 1 Expected sizes of PCR amplified bands with the above-listed primers

Target sequence	Accession number	Fwd. primer name	Rev. primer name	Fragment length, bp
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA2	LT991640	571Up	1325Do	755
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA2	LT991640	571Up	1850Do	1277
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA2	LT991640	571Up	2515Do	1942
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA2	LT991640	951Up	1850Do	897
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA2	LT991640	951Up	2515Do	1562
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA2	LT991640	1724Up	2515Do	792
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	123Up	847do	835
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	123Up	1118DO	1007
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	123Up	1760DO	1645
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	123Up	1850DO	1739

Target sequence	Accession number	Fwd. primer name	Rev. primer name	Fragment length, bp
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	123Up	2671DO	2562
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	422up	1760Do	1335
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	422up	1850DO	1429
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	422up	2671DO	2252
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	422up	2546DO	2739
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	422up	3299Do	2876
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	622UP	1760Do	1161
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	622UP	1850DO	1255
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	622UP	2671DO	2078
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	622UP	2546DO	2565
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	622UP	3299Do	2702
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	826UP	1760Do	931
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	826UP	1850DO	1025
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	826UP	2671DO	1848
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	826UP	2546DO	2335
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	826UP	3299Do	2472
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	1568UP	2671DO	1106
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	1568UP	2546DO	1593
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	1568UP	3299Do	1730
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	1568UP	3865Do	2296
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	1568UP	4391Do	2822
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	2464UP	3299Do	834
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	2464UP	3865Do	1400
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	2464UP	4391Do	1926
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	2464UP	5103Do	2637
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	2546Up	3865Do	726
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	2546Up	4391Do	1252
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	2546Up	5103Do	1963
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	3140Up	3865Do	726
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	3140Up	4391Do	1252
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	3140Up	5103Do	1963
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	3530Up	4391Do	862
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	3530Up	5103Do	1573
CVF SwC-G15 3 RNA1	LT991639	4263Up	5103Do	840
CVF SwC-H RNA2	MG925373	1037	1409	863
CVF SwC-H RNA2	MG925373	1037	1038	3843
CVF SwC-H RNA2	MG925373	1039	1038	3709
CVF SwC-H RNA2	MG925373	1562	1038	2234
CVF SwC-H RNA1B	MG925372	1037	1038	6174
CVF SwC-H RNA1B	MG925372	930	952	1255
CVF SwC-H RNA1B	MG925372	930	932	1546
CVF SwC-H RNA1B	MG925372	930	935	1613
CVF SwC-H RNA1B	MG925372	930	953	2488
CVF SwC-H RNA1B	MG925372	930	1038	2621
CVF SwC-H RNA1B	MG925372	931	952	1216
CVF SwC-H RNA1B	MG925372	931	932	1507
CVF SwC-H RNA1B	MG925372	931	935	1574
CVF SwC-H RNA1B	MG925372	931	953	2449
CVF SwC-H RNA1B	MG925372	931	1038	2582
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	1037	1019	821
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	1037	1018	877
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	1037	1034	1013
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	1037	839	1324
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	1037	1038	6147
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	1083	1019	723
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	1083	1018	779
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	1083	1034	915
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	1083	839	1226
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	1083	1038	6049
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	840	821	2956
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	931	820	857

Target sequence	Accession number	Fwd. primer name	Rev. primer name	Fragment length, bp
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	931	952	1216
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	931	932	1507
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	931	953	2443
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	931	960	2500
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	931	1038	2577
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	823	820	781
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	823	952	1140
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	823	932	1431
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	823	953	2367
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	823	960	2424
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	823	1038	2501
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	822	952	808
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	822	932	1099
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	822	953	2035
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	822	960	2092
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	822	1038	2169
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	992	960	754
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1A	KX192388	992	1038	831
PrVF SwC-43 RNA2A	KX192391	1037	1010	822
PrVF SwC-43 RNA2A	KX192391	1037	1014	906
PrVF SwC-43 RNA2A	KX192391	1037	830	1418
PrVF SwC-43 RNA2A	KX192391	1037	870	1651
PrVF SwC-43 RNA2A	KX192391	954	953	1748
PrVF SwC-43 RNA2A	KX192391	1037	1038	3586
PrVF SwC-43 RNA2A	KX192391	954	1038	2031
PrVF SwC-43 RNA2A	KX192391	961	953	1671
PrVF SwC-43 RNA2A	KX192391	961	1038	1954
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	1037	1017	814
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	1037	1018	872
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	1037	1034	1008
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	1083	1017	721
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	1083	1018	779
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	1083	1038	6056
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	841	1034	739
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	838	952	2230
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	838	932	2521
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	931	952	1216
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	931	932	1507
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	931	834	2273
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	931	953	2450
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	931	960	2507
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	931	1038	2584
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	962	834	1295
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	962	953	1472
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	962	960	1529
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	962	1038	1606
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	993	953	743
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	993	960	800
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1B	KX192389	993	1038	877
PrVF SwC-43 RNA2B	KX192392	1037	1038	3449
PrVF SwC-43 RNA2B	KX192392	1037	1010	842
PrVF SwC-43 RNA2B	KX192392	1037	830	1438
PrVF SwC-43 RNA2B	KX192392	829	818	1748
PrVF SwC-43 RNA2B	KX192392	829	953	1894
PrVF SwC-43 RNA2B	KX192392	829	960	1951
PrVF SwC-43 RNA2B	KX192392	829	1038	2028
PrVF SwC-43 RNA2B	KX192392	959	818	1642
PrVF SwC-43 RNA2B	KX192392	959	953	1788
PrVF SwC-43 RNA2B	KX192392	959	960	1845
PrVF SwC-43 RNA2B	KX192392	959	1038	1922
PrVF SwC-43 RNA2B	KX192392	954	818	1594

Target sequence	Accession number	Fwd. primer name	Rev. primer name	Fragment length, bp
PrVF SwC-43 RNA2B	KX192392	954	953	1740
PrVF SwC-43 RNA2B	KX192392	954	960	1797
PrVF SwC-43 RNA2B	KX192392	954	1038	1874
PrVF SwC-43 RNA2B	KX192392	819	960	756
PrVF SwC-43 RNA2B	KX192392	819	1038	833
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1C	KX192390	1037	1018	865
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1C	KX192390	1037	1034	1001
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1C	KX192390	871	1018	847
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1C	KX192390	871	1034	983
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1C	KX192390	1083	1018	775
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1C	KX192390	1083	1034	911
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1C	KX192390	841	1034	739
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1C	KX192390	1150	952	1371
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1C	KX192390	1150	932	1662
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1C	KX192390	1150	933	1671
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1C	KX192390	927	952	1300
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1C	KX192390	927	932	1591
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1C	KX192390	927	933	1600
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1C	KX192390	931	952	1216
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1C	KX192390	931	932	1507
PrVF SwC-43 RNA1C	KX192390	931	933	1516
PrVF SwC-43 RNA2C	KX192393	1037	1010	819
PrVF SwC-43 RNA2C	KX192393	1037	1038	3740
PrVF SwC-43 RNA2C	KX192393	1037	830	1415
PrVF SwC-43 RNA2C	KX192393	827	1009	703
PrVF SwC-43 RNA2C	KX192393	827	830	1200
PrVF SwC-43 RNA2C	KX192393	958	957	1951
PrVF SwC-43 RNA2C	KX192393	958	953	1985
PrVF SwC-43 RNA2C	KX192393	958	1038	2437
PrVF SwC-43 RNA2C	KX192393	829	957	1856
PrVF SwC-43 RNA2C	KX192393	829	953	1890
PrVF SwC-43 RNA2C	KX192393	829	1038	2342
PrVF SwC-43 RNA2C	KX192393	954	957	1702
PrVF SwC-43 RNA2C	KX192393	954	953	1736
PrVF SwC-43 RNA2C	KX192393	954	1038	2188